

Research Article

Evaluation of a New Generation Diesel Engine Forklift in Terms of Noise Emissions

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Abstract

Forklifts (Counterbalance) are work machines that are used to carry and stack specialized or standardized loads with a special attachment connection adapted to the mast section according to the type of work to be done. Forklifts have different load lifting capacities and optional lifting heights. These vehicles cannot reach high speeds due to their nature and safety. According to the development of autonomous driving worldwide, a rapid development is observed in both technology and comfort parameters of warehouse transportation equipment. In the comfort-oriented evaluations of diesel forklifts, the noises originating from the combustion in the engine and the motion transmission in the mechanical units are the main ones; in addition, the noises originating from the wheel and road irregularities constitute the secondary noises originating from the imbalance in the mast system. In this study, the change in the internal and external noise measurements, i.e. the operator and the environment, of a new generation diesel engine forklift according to the ANSI/ITSDF B56 standard was examined. In the unloaded driving evaluation, it was determined that the noise emitted to the environment was 8% less than the noise coming to the operator. In the evaluation of the noise emitted to the environment, it was determined that the idle speed under no-load conditions was 20.7% lower than the maximum speed noise level. In the evaluation of the noise coming to the operator; it was determined that the effect of the load lifted at low speeds was 2.7% higher than the no-load condition, and that the idle speed was 17.6% lower than the maximum speed noise level under the same load condition.

Keywords: Forklift, Forklift Noise, NVH, Euro V Noise, ANSI/ITSDF B56.

1. Introduction

A forklift (Counterbalance), which is one of the types of special-purpose construction machinery, is a transport, lifting and loading machine that is used to transport and stack any load to a certain distance by picking up and lifting it with forked arms. In ports, warehouses, storages, factories and airports; they are machines that work economically in jobs such as storage, stocking and warehousing. These machines are used for material loading, unloading and transportation services. It is also used for fast solution of specialized works with special attachment connection adapted to the mast part according to the type of work to be done [1].

Governments are taking serious steps to reduce pollutant emission rates worldwide. Our country also supports these steps with international agreements signed. The forklift sector, like all other sectors, is renewing itself in this field, that is, in the direction of reducing polluting exhaust emissions. In this context, one of the most important developments in our country has been the transition to the use of internal combustion engine forklifts with EURO V exhaust emission level in the industry. With the after-treatment system added to the internal combustion engine within the scope of compliance with the renewed pollutant emission levels, more environmentally friendly, less polluting exhaust emissions and quieter forklifts are used in the market. The after treatment system is a device used to reduce harmful exhaust emissions from internal combustion engines and to ensure that engines meet the values in exhaust emission regulations. Changes in noise due to the effect of this after-treatment system constitute the main source of comfort parameters in forklift.

When the literature is examined; in a study conducted by Demir and Demir (2024), it was determined that fully electric forklifts have significantly lower noise levels in internal and external noise measurements compared to diesel engine forklifts, according to the ANSI/ITSDF B56 standard [1].

In a study conducted by Kim (2008) and colleagues, noise sources for an industrial forklift were identified and noise and vibration were reduced [2].

In a study conducted by Kim and Chung (2008), evaluated the reduction of acoustic noise generated by electromagnetic force in an induction motor of the electrical forklift [3].

In this study, internal and external noise measurements of a new generation diesel engine forklift (Figure 1) are carried out according to the ANSI/ITSDF B56 standard.

Figure 1: Tümosan New Generation Forklift ALF-D

2. Materials and Methods

Forklifts are designed by correctly integrating multiple subsystems together forklift (Figure 2). These subsystems are shown in different colours below.

Figure 2: Forklift Subsystems

In this study, a TÜMOSAN brand forklift with a new generation diesel engine and a load lifting capacity of 3.5 tons will be used. The technical specifications of this forklift are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Technical Specifications

Specifications	
Power type	Diesel
Rated capacity (kg)	3500
Load center (mm)	500
Wheelbase (mm)	1750
Weight	
Forklift weight, unladen (kg)	4870
Unladen axle, front/rear (kg)	1970/2900
Laden axle, front/rear (kg)	7900/470
Tyres	
Tyre, front	28x9-15
Tyre, rear	6.50-10
Number of wheels, front/rear (x=driven)	2x/2
Track width, front (mm)	1030
Track width, rear (mm)	985
Overall dimensions	
Mast tilt angle, front/rear	6/8
Mast lowered height (mm)	2120
Mast extended height (mm)	4500
Overhead guard height (mm)	2170
length to face of fork(with fork) (mm)	3900
length to face of fork(without fork) (mm)	2750
Overall width (mm)	1250
Fork size (L, W, T) (mm)	45/125/1200
Turning radius (mm)	2450
Performance	
Travel Speed, laden/unladen (km/h)	19/20
Lifting speed, laden/unladen (mm/s)	420/460
Lowering speed, laden/unladen (mm/s)	450/500
Gradeability, laden (%)	20
Brake System	Hydraulic
Engine	
Engine power (kW@rpm)	41@2500
Maximum torque (Nm@rpm)	190@1600

In this section; ANSI/ITSDF B56 test standard, test conditions, equipment and calibration procedures, test track and test-related visuals are given. This standard is used to evaluate the noise levels of forklifts under conditions close to actual use.

2.1. ANSI/ITSDF B56 Test Standard

Noise measurement standard for fully electric and internal combustion engine-driven industrial vehicles for low lift, high lift and rough terrain operation. The test procedures specified in this standard are the basis for determining the contribution of powered industrial trucks to the overall sound level of a selected work area. Tests can be carried out on trucks both in motion and in a static state and, where appropriate, with the lifting gear in operation [4].

Noise Measurement Test Area: The prescribed test measurement environment requires an acoustic environment that can only be achieved in a large open space or a semi- or anechoic chamber. If an outdoor test site is used, a flat open area without slopes is required. The test site must not contain large reflective surfaces. An area of concrete, sealed asphalt or similar hard material with a center radius of 10 m (33 ft) and a radius of not less than 50 m (165 ft) will be acceptable. There should be no significant obstacles within a 30 m (100 ft) radius of the truck (Figure 3) [4].

Figure 3: Test Area

Operating conditions of forklift: All parts of the drive and lift systems (i.e. hydraulic system, electric motor and gearboxes in trucks powered by an internal combustion engine) must reach a constant operating temperature for the previous ambient conditions. All auxiliary equipment (i.e. auxiliary attachments) that would normally operate during the duty cycle must be operational during the sound measurements.

Test Load: The truck shall be loaded or unloaded as required for the specific tests. When a test load is specified in the test procedure, the load shall be 70% of the equipped truck capacity [4].

Operator's work: The operator shall be in normal driving mode. There shall be no observers in close proximity to the driver, forklift or cab (if applicable) during the taking of measurements. Observers shall be away from and behind the microphones used during the specific test. Operators shall not wear abnormally sound absorbing clothing [4].

Placement and Direction of Microphones: Sound level measurements shall be made with the microphone located 50 mm horizontally from the operator's right or left ear. The side indicating the higher sound level shall be used.

Test Procedure and Measurements: At least three cycles shall be performed at each microphone position for each test cycle or element of a test cycle. For each microphone position, the arithmetic mean of the two highest values within 2 dB of each other is used as the reported sound level [4].

Measurement of Sound of the Operator's workplace

Test Method 1: With the truck stationary and loaded, in the mast lowered position, fully tilted back and fully retracted, the maximum achievable lifting speed should be selected, where possible. The maximum readings in dB should be recorded.

Test Method 2: When the truck is stationary, idling, the engine is started for 1 minute, during which the highest measured value is noted. This test mode is not required for full electric trucks.

Test Method 3: In the unloaded state, with the truck driving and at maximum speed, the maximum measured value in both forward and reverse gears is recorded.

Test Method 4: In the loaded state, with the truck in drive and at maximum speed, the maximum measured value in both forward and reverse gears is noted.

Measurement of Environmental Noise

Forklift in Motion Test: The horizontal distance from the microphone to the near side of the truck will be 7 m. The path of the center line of the truck shall follow the CC line as closely as possible from line AA to line BB. The distance between AA and BB shall not be less than 20 m and the microphone shall not be less than 10 m from both (Figure 4). The microphones shall be located 1.2 m above ground level and oriented according to the manufacturer's instructions for the smoothest response characteristics. The tests shall be carried out with no load [4].

Figure 4: Microphone Location (For Test With Forklift Motion)

Test with Forklift Stationary: For fixed tests, sound level measurements should normally be made at a distance of 7 m from the centers of the four main surfaces of the equipment, with the microphone 1.2 m above ground level. In general, the four main surfaces refer to the front, back and sides of an imaginary box that exactly fits the machine and mast but does not include the forks (Figure 5).

With the mast lowered and fully tilted back, the maximum lifting speed achievable with an unladen forklift truck will be selected where appropriate. Readings shall be recorded before the mast reaches a standstill during the lifting operation. A minimum of three cycles will be run at each microphone position. Recorded readings shall not include unusual transient or similar atypical noises [4].

Figure 5: Test Site Arrangement – Microphone Location
(For Test With Forklift Stationary)

3. Results

The ANSI/ITSDF B56 noise measurement standard for the assessment of noise levels in the forklift industry was applied in this assessment. Noise is defined as a disturbing sound that is unpleasant to hear and has a high sound level. Therefore, minimizing the sound level of each sound generating system that includes human beings allows the work to be done in a healthy, safe and high quality. During the noise test, the test site was made suitable for noise measurement. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the test site prepared for the operations to be performed during the test.

Figure 6: Forklift Test Site View

Figure 7: Forklift Test Site View 2

In addition, the test area for measuring the environmental noise is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Forklift Test View

According to the standard, 4 test procedures were applied to measure the noise to the operator. Details of these procedures are given in the materials and methods section. In the category of noise to the operator, we analyzed the noise values of a 70% loaded forklift truck, which we call test method I. To generate these values, 10 tests are performed (Figure 9). When these values are averaged, it is found that the loaded noise levels diesel forklift are 86,35 dB. Forklift mast systems are divided into 2 as duplex and triplex. In triplex models, when the middle cylinder completes its stroke, it creates extra noise while passing to the side cylinders. This model triplex model mast system.

Figure 9: Test Method I Noise Measurement

In the category of noise to the operator, the noise values to the operator are analyzed while the forklift is idling, which we call test method II. For this 6 tests are performed (Figure 10). The average noise level of the diesel truck was measured as 69,2 dB.

Figure 10: Test Method II Noise Measurement

In the category of noise to the operator, noise values are measured in the no-load condition, which we characterized as test method III, when the truck is driving and operating in both forward and reverse gears at maximum speed. The differences in no-load driving conditions for forward and reverse are close to each other. The average of forward driving tests is 85,7 dB and the average of reverse driving is 94,9 dB (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Test Method III Noise Measurement

In the category of noise to the operator, noise values are measured in the loaded condition, which we characterized as test method IV, when the truck is driving and operating in both forward and reverse gears at maximum speed. There is a minimum 5 dB difference in noise caused by the reverse warning horn when driving backwards compared to driving forward. The effect of the carried load on noise is not significant. The average of forward driving tests is 86,1 dB and the average of reverse driving is 93,5 dB (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Test Method IV Noise Measurement

In additional test I the noise to the operator, it is the lifting of the mast with and without load while the forklift is idling. It has been determined that the impact of the load lifted while idling is 2.7% higher than the unloaded situation (Figure 13).

Figure 13: In Additional Test I Noise Measurement

In additional test 2, the noise to the operator is the lifting of the mast system at idle and maximum speed under the same load condition. It was found that the idle speed was 17.6% lower than the maximum speed noise level under the same load condition (Figure 14).

Figure 14: In Additional Test II Noise Measurement

In accordance with the standard, 2 test procedures are applied to measure the noise emitted to the environment. Details of these procedures are given in the materials and methods section. In the category of ambient noise, the noise values are measured over microphones located 7 m away while an unloaded forklift truck, which we characterize as test method I, passed between 2 specific points at maximum speed. A sufficient number of tests are performed to generate these values (Figure 15). When these values are averaged, it is found that the unloaded noise levels diesel forklift are 78,7 dB.

Figure 15: Test Method I Noise to the Environmental Measurement

In the category of environmental noise, test method II measured the noise levels of an unloaded forklift truck as it passed through the maximum peak of the elevator speed, using microphones located 7 m away. Three tests are performed to generate these values (Figure 16). When these values are averaged, it is found that the unloaded noise levels diesel forklift are 78,8 dB.

Figure 16: Test Method II Noise to the Enviromental Measurement

In both test cases, the measured values of microphone 2 are higher for the noise coming from the environment. This may be due to its proximity to the exhaust side or to the less insulated area of the noise outlet from the main noise source. It is determined that the values measured from microphone number 2 are 1.4% higher than the values measured from microphone number 1.

In additional test 3, the noise to the environment is the lifting of the mast system at idle and maximum speed under without load condition. It is found that the idle speed is 20,7% lower than the maximum speed noise level under the without load condition (Figure 17).

Figure 17: In Additional Test III Measurement

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The transformation to green energy in the world will undoubtedly shape the future of the forklift industry. The fact that forklifts with Euro V emission levels can be used by countries today does not mean that this cannot be increased to a more challenging emission level in the future. Therefore, companies should aim to both develop their products and keep user comfort at the highest level during the possible transformation process.

In this study, the changes in the internal and external noise measurements of a new generation diesel engine forklift, i.e. the noise emitted to the operator and the environment, are examined according to the ANSI/ITSDF B56 standard.

In the unloaded driving evaluation, it is determined that the noise emitted to the environment is 8% less than the noise coming to the operator. In the evaluation of the noise emitted to the environment, it is determined that the idling speed under no-load

condition is 20.7% lower than the maximum speed noise level. In the evaluation of the noise coming to the operator, it is determined that the effect of the load lifted at low speeds was 2.7% higher than the unloaded situation, and that the idle speed is 17.6% lower than the maximum speed noise level under the same load condition.

As a continuation of this study, the internal and external noise levels of fully electric forklifts, one of the most important actors of the possible transformation process, can be determined and compared with forklifts operated with other power sources.

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References

- [1] DEMİR, M., & DEMİR, A. (2024). Dizel motorlu ve tam elektrikli forkliftlerin çalışma parametreleri açısından kıyaslanması. Yüksek Lisans Tezi,
- [2] Kim, W. H., Hong, I. H., & Chung, J. T. (2008). A study on noise reduction for the driving system of a forklift. *Transactions of the Korean Society for Noise and Vibration Engineering*, 18(1), 80-86.
- [3] Kim, W. H., & Chung, J. T. (2009). A Study on the Characteristic of Noise and Vibration in 3-phase Induction Motor for the Forklift. *Transactions of the Korean Society for Noise and Vibration Engineering*, 19(1), 3-9.
- [4] ANSI/ITSDF-B56 (2013). Measurements of Sound Emitted by Low Lift, High Lift and Rough Terrain Powered Industrial Trucks. American National Standard, USA.